

CHALLENGES AND ASPECTS OF STUDYING THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE IN SCHOOLS

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Annotation. The article is devoted to the integration of the educational process, in particular the relationship and interdependence of the Russian language and literature. Teachers of the Russian language and literature must remember the ever-increasing international importance of the Russian language and literature and must help students successfully apply the skills acquired in the classroom.

Keywords: phonetics, grammar, punctuation, intersubject connections, gender, number, cases, declension, stress, suffix, stress, prefix, parts of speech.

The Russian language ranks sixth in the world in terms of the number of speakers, and about three hundred million people speak it. The mighty Russian language is rich and difficult to learn.

Even the letters in words are not always written as “heard” and there is no definite explanation for this; the rule of reading stressed and unstressed vowels saves. However, stress in Russian is not fixed; it can be located at the beginning, middle or end of a sentence, sometimes even in all places (double / triple stress).

Declensions are another complexity - 6 cases, taking into account three genders, four variant stems and the presence of special forms for the plural, one and a half hundred variant endings. Declension of numerals is an equally difficult task (eight hundred rubles or eight hundred rubles?).

Changing number, gender, case of adjectives and nouns, verb conjugations, prefixes, endings and suffixes - it is not easy even for Russian-speaking schoolchildren to fully master all the subtleties. In addition to everything, there are an abundance of exception words that do not obey the general rules. Dictionary words in the Russian language can cause great difficulties - these are mainly words whose spelling cannot be checked; they need to be memorized.

The difference in the formation and use of perfect and imperfect verbs is confusion in endings. Difficulties arise with words that have a similar sound, but different spellings and meanings, as well as words with the same spelling but different meanings. Don't forget about words that change meaning when the emphasis changes.

More difficulties:

1. Russian is a synthetic language, which leads to a large number of word forms and free word order in a sentence.
2. in the Russian language there are many synonymous words, often significantly different in shades of meaning.
3. abundance of prefixes and suffixes.
4. frequently occurring hissing and whistling phonemes.

Knowing all this, you shouldn't be surprised when foreigners compare Russian and Chinese.

Every teacher faces an urgent task: to bring theory closer to practice, to teach their students to use the knowledge they have, and to connect learning with life. To solve this problem, the implementation of interdisciplinary connections is of great importance, in this case, between the Russian language and literature, between which, as subjects of teaching, there is an organic, natural, inextricable connection. Working for a long time at school, we try to make this connection at all stages where possible.

When studying phonetics, we strive to develop students' good diction and clear pronunciation. Good diction is the first condition for expressive reading in any school. Work on diction begins with the study of phonetics and continues for a number of years. We instill in students that clear reading is the key to competent writing, that clear speech is always more expressive and convincing than slurred pater. When studying phonetics, you often have to test the pronunciation of some sibilants. When studying the participle, we prevent errors that arise in cases when students form a participle from reflexive verbs without the particle - *sya*.

For example: Gavrilu barely waited for Chelkash. The rest went home. A lot of work has to be done on setting the accent. Children say this: Youth felt hatred for the enemy... Tolstoy wrote a novel... This statue is much more beautiful... The emphasis is placed incorrectly on individual words (*arrest, leisure, carpenter, means, etc.*) Correct stress is practiced in Russian language and literature lessons. When reading a new text, during student responses, you need to be especially careful in this regard, since children, learning terms that are new to them, often make mistakes. In connection with the dialectal stress - LOG - in the words I will put, I will add, I will offer, it is necessary to carry out painstaking work, and gradually children learn that without a prefix this verb is not used at all, that its option for the imperative form is to put, that the emphasis on the root - LOG - in the verb falls only in some forms of the future tense.

Grammar gives students rules, but the meaning and forms of words are clearly perceived only in coherent speech. In expressive reading, this indicates syntactic blindness. The student does not see the signs, and the writer's thought does not reach him, or it does reach him with great distortions. The student reads an excerpt from Tatyana's letter to Onegin and pauses not according to signs, but according to the lines of the poem.

I am writing to you - what more?

II What more can I say?

II Now, I know, in your will II, etc.

The inability to see signs and incorrect logical stress distorted the meaning of a beautiful work. The main thing in reading is the ability to find logical emphasis, penetrate into an idea, convey it, and among children there is still a belief that the main thing in reading is pathos. Incorrect reading, as a rule, entails syntactic illiteracy and vice versa. Students learn punctuation in language lessons, but it becomes alive for them in literature lessons. Here they feel the difference between correct and incorrect speech, here they understand their mistakes. In literature lessons, students often encounter incomprehensible words, and therefore, when preparing for lessons, I carefully review the sections of the textbook and do vocabulary work. Especially a lot of notes have to be taken when studying works: "The Tale of Igor's Campaign", "The Minor", "Woe from Wit", "Fathers and Sons", etc. In high school, vocabulary work is done orally and by taking notes during commented reading. For a number of years, for each literary topic, I have been selecting words that are not entirely clear to children or are difficult to write. With these words they make up separate sentences or include them in the texts of the

presentation. When working on an essay plan, I make sure to repeat the types of simple sentences and ensure that the plan is correctly formatted. For dictations and training exercises, you should always try to give a text that meets two conditions: 1) that the text contains the necessary grammatical material; 2) this text complemented and expanded students' understanding of the literary topic. So, we, teachers of the Russian language and literature, must remember the ever-increasing international importance of the Russian language and literature, and must help students successfully apply the skills acquired in the classroom.

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